

Possible Antiparkinsonian Compounds—Part XII Synthesis of Some Quinazolone Derivatives

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2-Aryl-3, 1(4H)-benzoxazin-(4)-one/2-aryl-6 : 8-dibromo-3, 1(4H)-benzoxazin(4H)-one/2-aryl-6-bromo-3, 1(4H)-benzoxazin(4)-one and monoethanolamine were condensed to yield 2-aryl-[3-(hydroxyethyl)]-3, 1(4H)-quinazolin-4-one/2-aryl-6 : 8-dibromo-[3-(hydroxyethyl)]-3, 1(4H), quinazolin-4-one/2-aryl-6-bromo-[3-(hydroxyethyl)]-3, 1(4H) quinazolin-4-one. These compounds were further condensed with the compounds containing active hydrogen atoms employing Mannich-reaction type method.

QUINAZOLONE derivatives show a wide variety of physiological and pharmacological properties such as central nervous system depressant^{1,18}, anticonvulsant^{4,5}, anticarcinogenic⁶, musclerelaxant^{6,7} and antiparkinsonian⁸. In view of these observations, it was thought worthwhile to synthesize some newer quinazolone derivatives with a view to testing their antiparkinsonian activity.

The synthesis was accomplished along the following route :

Where X = H ; Br

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillaries in sulphuric acid melting point bath and are uncorrected.

5-bromo/3:5-dibromo-anthranilic acid (I) : This was obtained following the method of Rosanoff et al⁹.

2-Phenyl-3,1-(4H)-benzoxazin-4-one/2-phenyl-6 : 8-dibromo-3,1-(4H)-benzoxazin-4-one/2-phenyl-6-bromo-3, 1-(4H) benzoxazin-4-one (III)

The procedure described by Sammour et al¹¹ was followed. Thus anthranilic acid/3 : 5-dibromo-anthranilic acid (0.01 mole) was dissolved in pyridine (30 ml). The solution was cooled and benzoyl-chloride (0.0 mole) was added dropwise with constant shaking. After the addition was complete, the mixture was further stirred for half an hour at room temperature. It was then treated with sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) to remove any unreacted acid. When the effervescence ceased, it was filtered and washed repeatedly with water in order to remove adhered pyridine. It was recrystallised from dilute ethanol.

2-Phenyl [-3-(hydroxyethyl)]-3,1 (4H)-quinazolin-4-one/2-phenyl-6 : 8-dibromo-[3-(hydroxyethyl)]-3,1 (4H)-quinazolin-4-one/2-phenyl-6-bromo-[3-(hydroxyethyl)]-3,1(4H)-quinazolin-4-one (III)

A mixture of 2-phenyl-3, 1 (4H)-benzoxazin-4-one/2-phenyl-6 : 8-dibromo-3, 1 (4H)-benzoxazin-4-one (0.01 mole) and monoethanol amine (0.01 mole) in 30 ml. of dry pyridine was refluxed for 6 hours and the reaction mixture was poured in ice cooled dil. HCl. The solid product that separated out, was repeatedly washed with water and recrystallized from dilute ethanol. Various compounds thus synthesized are recorded in Table 1.

2-Phenyl-3(arylethyl) quinazolin-(3H)-4-one/2-phenyl-6 : 8-dibromo-3-(arylethyl)-quinazolin-(3H)-4-

one/2-phenyl-6-bromo-3-(arylethyl)-quinazolin-(3H)-4-one (IV)

TABLE 1

Sl. No	X	X ¹	M. P.	Molecular formula	Analysis Calcd.	Found
1.	H	H	160	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	10.50	10.23
2.	Br	Br	180	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Br ₂	6.01	6.21
3.	Br	H	194	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ Br	8.11	8.23

Note : The above compounds were recrystallized from ethanol. The yield ranged from 60-70%.

A mixture of the reactive hydrogen compound (0.005 mole), the above quinazolinone (0.005 mole) (III) and a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid was dissolved in 30 ml. of ethanol and refluxed for 3 hours. After removing ethanol by distillation, a crude product was obtained, which was washed with water and then recrystallized from a polar solvent. The compounds thus synthesized are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	X	X ¹	R	M. P. ^o	Molecular formula	Analysis Nitrogen	
						Calcd.	Found
1.	H	H	benzamido	174	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	11.38	11.00
2.	H	H	phthalimido	170	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	10.60	10.25
3.	H	H	succinimido	170	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	12.10	11.85
4.	H	H	α-(β-naphthyl)	186	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂	7.10	7.66
5.	H	H	3 : 4-dihydroxyphenyl	180	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂	7.85	8.00
6.	H	H	α-(phenolyl)	173	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂		
7.	Br	Br	benzamido	195	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ Br	8.00	7.95
8.	Br	Br	(phenolyl)	192	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	5.58	5.5
9.	Br	Br	α-(β-naphthyl)	189	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	5.09	5.10
10.	Br	Br	succinimido	186	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	7.98	7.51
11.	Br	Br	phthalimido	188	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ Br ₂	7.76	7.22
12.	Br	H	succinimido	184	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ Br	9.83	9.52
13.	Br	H	phthalimido	175	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂ Br	10.40	10.11

Note : The solvent used for the recrystallization was ethanol. The yield ranged from 50-60%.

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